

Mouth Larva: Frequently asked questions

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A mouth larva refers to the larvae of certain fly species that infest the mouth, also known as **oral myiasis**. This is a rare condition in humans but can be serious if left untreated.

Here's a breakdown of your questions:

- **Mouth Larva/Oral Myiasis:** This occurs when fly maggots live inside the mouth. House flies, blow flies, and flesh flies are the most common culprits. These flies lay eggs on open wounds, decaying tissue, or even healthy tissues in some cases, especially among people with poor hygiene or weakened immune systems. The hatched larvae feed on the tissue, causing irritation, pain, and bleeding.
- **Oral Myiasis due to Chrysomya Bezziana:** This is a specific type of oral myiasis caused by the *Chrysomya bezziana* fly. This fly is common in tropical and subtropical regions and is known to lay eggs in wounds or orifices, including the mouth. The larvae can cause significant tissue damage and even spread infections.
- **Symptoms of Myiasis:** Symptoms of myiasis can vary depending on the location and severity of the infestation. In general, symptoms include:
 - Pain and irritation in the affected area
 - Bleeding
 - Swelling
 - Bad breath
 - Visible maggots in the mouth
 - Feeling of movement under the skin (maggots moving)

If you suspect you or someone you know has myiasis, it's important to seek medical attention immediately. Early diagnosis and treatment can help prevent further complications.